

THE CRACK CLOSURE PHENOMENON IN FATIGUED CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY LAMINATES

M. Wevers, I. Verpoest, P. De Meester and E. Aernoudt
(Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Department of Metallurgy and
Materials Engineering, de Croylaan 2, 3030 Leuven, Belgium)

ABSTRACT

This tension-tension fatigue study on cross plied laminates, revealed that the fatigue stress ratio R has a considerable influence on the damage development. For stress ratios smaller than 0.5 additional damage is introduced due to crack closure. This crack closure phenomenon is well known for metals, although it has for those materials a beneficial, crack growth retarding effect. In composites, it has not yet been recognized to influence the fatigue damage development. A micromechanical explanation has been found to explain the crack closure phenomenon in cfre composites, and it has been worked out in a mechanistic model.

INTRODUCTION

Fatigue microdamage studies are of primary importance to all material scientists and design engineers who are aiming towards a broader application of fibre reinforced plastics. Studies on fatigue damage found in literature definitely draw a good picture of the nature of fatigue damage in composite laminates. However, the micromechanical explanation for the development of fatigue damage is not always straightforward.

This paper describes the fatigue damage modes found in crossplied carbon-epoxy laminates $(0^{\circ}_2, 90^{\circ}_2)_S$ loaded in tension fatigue at two different stress ratios. The micromechanical explanation for the damage initiation and growth will also be covered, in which the importance of crack closure, a new concept for damage development in composites, will be revealed and detailed.

MATERIAL

Carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (cfre) prepreg layers, Fibredux 920C-TS-5-42 supplied by Ciba Geigy Co., were laminated into a $(0^{\circ}_2, 90^{\circ}_2)_S$ stacking sequence and cured in a pressclave resulting in a 1.16 mm thick laminate. Specimens, 19.8 x 128 mm, were cut from this laminate with a diamond saw. The edges of the laminate were polished up to 1 μm enabling damage studies at the edges with the optical microscope and the replica technique.

The fatigue tests were carried out on a servo hydraulic fatigue testing machine, Schenck Hydropuls 25 kN, in an air conditioned room at $20 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $45 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity. The frequency of the sinusoidal fatigue cycle was 3 Hz. For the same maximum fatigue stress of 70% of the UTS, namely $\sigma_{\text{max}} = 548 \text{ MN/m}^2$, two different test series have been carried out: series 1 with $R = \sigma_{\text{min}} / \sigma_{\text{max}} = 0.03$ and series 2 with $R = 0.5$. The former tests were carried out for 280000 cycles and the latter for 500000 cycles.

DAMAGE STUDY

1. Damage assessment techniques.

Three different nondestructive test techniques were used to monitor the damage initiation and development. These techniques are described in previous papers^{1,2,3} and will only briefly be mentioned here.

The *acoustic emission technique* was used to follow the initiation and growth of the distinct damage modes during fatigue. For this paper we will focus on the stress level at which the AE-events of the damage modes are generated.

At regular intervals, *replicas* were taken of the edges of the specimens. They were investigated under the light microscope, so that maps of matrix cracks and delaminations could be drawn. The replica, taken at the end of the fatigue test, was also studied with the scanning electron microscope.

X-ray radiographs were taken at the end of each test in order to visualize the internal damage state of the specimen. A solution of zinciodide was used as an enhancing agent penetrating under a low strain.

On top of this, *longitudinal stiffness degradation measurements* were carried out using a dynamic extensometer, Instron 2620 μ -601, with a gauge length of 100 mm. The hysteresis curves taken at several time intervals were carefully studied and a correlation with the fatigue damage was investigated.

2. Description of the fatigue damage.

On the X-ray radiograph taken at the end of the fatigue test the total length of matrix cracks as well as the total number of matrix cracks was counted: 76 matrix cracks with a total length of 165 mm for a test run at $R=0.5$ and 137 matrix cracks with a total length of 570 mm for a test run at $R=0.03$. It is thus clear that the fatigue damage state of the specimen tested at $R=0.5$ was less severe than the specimen tested at $R=0.03$, although the test was carried out for almost twice the number of fatigue cycles. The main damage mode seen on the radiographs was matrix cracking, but some matrix cracks as indicated in Fig. 1 are raveled. This raveled outlook indicates the presence of incipient delaminations (type 1) which follow the matrix cracks.

EDGE

Fig. 1 Raveled picture of the 90° matrix cracks.

In Fig. 2a and 2b the fatigue damage developed at the edges, as revealed by the replicas taken at the end of the test, is shown. For the specimen tested at $R=0.5$ (Fig. 2a) we notice the presence of full thickness matrix cracks in the 90° layers, small straight 90° cracks not fully grown over

the thickness of the specimen and very small edge delaminations (type 2) between the 90° and 0° layers. The damage state in the specimen tested at R=0.03 is more severe (Fig. 2b). More full thickness and small matrix cracks, sometimes at an angle to the other matrix cracks, can be found, whereas the edge delaminations (type 2) have grown over a longer length along the interfaces between the 0° and 90° plies.

Fig. 2: Fatigue damage on the replicas of the edges of the $(0^{\circ}_2, 90^{\circ}_2)_s$ specimens, taken at the end of the fatigue tests respectively at R=0.5 (a) and R=0.03 (b).

The results of the AE-measurements will be discussed on the basis of the graph of the AE-activity versus the stress level. On Fig. 3a and 3b it is obvious that in the upper stress region ($\sigma > 0.6 \sigma_{\max}$) the AE-activity is very similar for both test conditions. In the lower stress range of the R=0.5 test (Fig. 3a), the activity is slightly higher, peaking at the stress reversal. However, this activity remains 50% lower than the AE-activity in the lower stress range of the R=0.03 test (Fig. 3b). In other words, a major part of the AE-signals in the R=0.03 test are generated in the lower third of the stress cycle.

Fig. 3a: The number of AE-signals in function of the stress level for the fatigue test at R=0.5

Fig. 3b: The number of AE-signals in function of the stress level for the fatigue test at R=0.03

Finally the hysteresis curves for each test series have been compared. These curves reveal also information on the fatigue damage development. On the curves for the R=0.03 test (Fig. 4) one can see that the upper part of the σ - ϵ curves shifts parallel to itself but the lower part becomes convex towards the end of the fatigue test. For the curves of the R=0.5 test (Fig. 4) only a parallel shift of the whole curve is measured. From studies on metals it is well known that the shape of the σ - ϵ curve can give an indication of crack closure.

Fig. 4: Hysteresis curves of the fatigue tests at R=0.5 and R=0.03.

Bringing together all the experimental evidence, one could conclude that there are three indications for additional damage in the lower stress levels: the higher AE-activity when reaching the zero stress level, the additional damage found on the replicas and the radiographs of the

specimens tested at $R=0.03$, and the changing slope of the σ - ϵ curve when reaching the zero stress level.

MICROMECHANICS OF THE FATIGUE DAMAGE MODES

The micromechanics of the formation of small cracks at an angle to the full thickness matrix cracks and the formation of type 1 delaminations and longer type 2 delaminations in the $(0^\circ_2, 90^\circ_2)_s$ laminates, will now be discussed. In our opinion the concept of **crack closure** provides a sound explanation for this additional damage found in the specimens tested at $R=0.03$.

Fig. 5: Model for the damage modes caused at crack closure of the perpendicular matrix cracks (a) and the inclined matrix cracks (b) in the 90° plies.

During the growth of 90° cracks, material debris is formed between the crack faces. This excess material causes compressive forces in the 90° plies for perpendicular cracks (Fig. 5a) or sliding forces for inclined matrix cracks (Fig. 5b) when the crack closes down. As the shear strength is low, matrix cracks parallel with the plane of maximum shear stress can be formed. It can be demonstrated that for a similar reason, larger dela-

minations at the edge (type 2) and delaminations (type 1) inside the laminate will be formed along these 90° cracks. This is due to the τ_{xy} and σ_z stresses in the interface between the 0° and 90° plies caused by crack closure of the 90° cracks. For the tests at R=0.5 the crack will stay open and no delaminations or shear cracks can be formed in the low stress level. All these additional damage modes, formed during the lower part of the sinusoidal load function, will cause acoustic emission at low stress levels; Fig. 3b confirmed this. The crack closure phenomenon also explains the convex part of the hysteresis curves. At crack closure there are compressive forces in the 90° plies around the matrix crack, but the 0° plies experience hereby tensile stresses. So deforming again from σ_{min} , smaller additional loads are needed to obtain any deformation than when the closed crack was not present or already open.

CONCLUSION

The tension-tension fatigue behaviour of $(0^{\circ}_2, 90^{\circ}_2)_s$ laminates for two different stress ratios R is documented in this paper. The fatigue damage studies performed, indicated a difference in damage state which is quite important in view of residual mechanical properties of these laminates. Crack closure, which is a well known phenomenon in fatigue of metals, plays an important role in the fatigue damage development of this type of laminate, fatigued at a stress ratio $R < 0.5$. A revolutionary mechanistic model was worked out to explain the crack closure phenomenon.

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